

Codebook ▾

Data Dictionary Codebook

11/01/2022 10:09

[^ Collapse all instruments](#)

#	Variable / Field Name	Field Label <i>Field Note</i>	Field Attributes (Field Type, Validation, Choices, Calculations, etc.)				
Instrument: Hfa Section 1 Key Hospital Statistics And Historical Facts (hfa_section_1_key_hospital_statistics_and_historical_facts) ^ Collapse							
1	alert_id	ALERT ID	text				
2	username		text Field Annotation: @USERNAME @READONLY @HIDDEN				
3	s1q1_nam	Section Header: <i>SECTION 1. Key hospital statistics and historical facts</i> 1. Respondent name	text, Required				
4	s1q2_tit	2. Respondent title	text, Required				
5	s1q3_oth	3. Was there anyone else in the meeting? Provide name(s) and position(s).	text				
6	s1q4_hos	4. Official hospital name	text, Required				
7	s1q5_year	5. Year of creation of hospital	text (number), Required				
8	s1q6nicu	6. Does this hospital have a NICU?	yesno <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
9	s1q6_ynic Show the field ONLY if: [s1q6nicu] = '1'	6a. Year when NICU added:	text (number), Required				
10	s1q7_lat	Section Header: <i>GPS coordinates:</i> 7. Latitude	text, Required Field Annotation: @LATITUDE				
11	s1q8_lon	8. Longitude	text, Required Field Annotation: @LONGITUDE				
12	s1q9_own	9. Owner	text, Required				
13	s1q10_ope	10. Operating authority	text, Required				
14	s1q11_leg	11. Legal status	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Public</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Faith based</td> </tr> </table>	1	Public	2	Faith based
1	Public						
2	Faith based						
15	s1q12_bed	12. Total number of beds <i># of beds for the entire hospital including maternity (number of patients might exceed this capacity - we will capture this later on with specific questions)</i>	text (number), Required				
16	s1q13_cat	13. Catchment area (radius, names of districts served, etc) <i>Put the information available taking and provide comments or details necessary to understand the data provided.</i>	text, Required				
17	s1q14_pop	14. Catchment population <i>Put the information available taking and provide comments or details necessary to understand the data provided.</i>	text (number), Required				
18	s1q15_ref	15. Referring health facilities (number by level) (e.g. 32 health centers, 150 health units)	text, Required				
19	s1q16_comm	16. Comments - please note any other points from the conversation	text, Required				

20	s1q17_hist	<p>17. Can you tell me briefly some of the key historical moments for this hospital? For example, inaugurations or building of additional wards, a big donation to the hospital, a change of location, an accident, a trial in the court, staff strikes etc. Start from the most obvious that you know or that is reported by staff, managers or community members. Complete with any documents you are provided with (brochure, etc) or website presenting the history of the hospital. Do not forget big changes that may have been recently introduced because of COVID19 such as closure of certain wards, appointment as a COVID19 treatment center and big reallocation of staff and occupation of the space etc.</p> <p><i>The events maybe many. Give priority to the events that have link with maternal and perinatal health that happened in the last 5 years. It should not take more than 15mn. We want the high-level events. The big changes from the helicopter perspective. As it possible to go back, and ask further questions if necessary.</i></p>	notes, Required						
21	hfa_section_1_key_hospital_statistics_and_historical_facts_complete	<p>Section Header: <i>Form Status</i></p> <p>Complete?</p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete
0	Incomplete								
1	Unverified								
2	Complete								
<p>Instrument: Hfa Section 2 General Hospital Governance And Finance (hfa_section_2_general_hospital_governance_and_finance) ^ Collapse</p>									
22	s2q1_nam	<p>Section Header: <i>SECTION 2. General hospital governance and financing</i></p> <p>1. Respondent name</p> <p><i>If the same as for section 2, just copy and paste; don't ask again</i></p>	text, Required						
23	s2q2_tit	<p>2. Respondent title</p> <p><i>. If the same as for section 2, just copy and paste; don't ask again</i></p>	text, Required						
24	s2q3_oth	<p>3. Was there anyone else in the meeting? Provide name(s) and position(s)</p> <p><i>If the same as for section 2, just copy and paste; don't ask again.</i></p>	text						
25	s2q4_gov	<p>4. Could you explain the governance structure which is in place in this hospital?</p> <p>Probes: Can you tell me about the key people in this hospital (name) and their roles? For example, administrative manager and/or clinical manager? How long (number of years or year started) have these people (director/manager) been in their function? What decision-making powers do they have? Who oversees the managers (board, district, MOH, etc)? What committees are set up to guide? Do they involve civil society or community representatives? From whom do you get directives? What is the influence of the central system, eg. the Ministry of Health? What is the influence from the local governance structure? Note names, function/titles and number of year in this function</p> <p><i>Note names, function/titles and number of year in this function.</i></p>	notes, Required						
26	s2q5_dec1	<p>5. As a manager of this hospital, what is your ability to make your own decisions?</p> <p>Probes: Let's take the example of extending the maternity wing of this hospital: From whom do you need to get permission? How could you finance this? What are potential resources you could tap from local financing mechanisms, the local governance, the national funding schemes?</p>	notes, Required						
27	s2q6_dec2	<p>6. As a manager of this hospital, what is your ability to make your own decisions?</p> <p><i>Let's take another example, you want to employ additional staff: what is the procedure for employment? Do you have own resources? Do you need permission from the central government? From the local governance? Can you advertise, who will decide? Who will sign the contract?</i></p>	notes, Required						
28	s2q7_kpm	<p>7. Now, can you tell me who are the key people in regard to the maternity ward?</p> <p>For example, the doctor in charge, the head midwife, the head of the NICU, etc? How long have these people been in their functions?</p> <p><i>Note names, function/titles and number of year in this function.</i></p>	notes, Required						

29	s2q8_fin	8. How is the hospital financed? <i>List most important sources of income and % (approximate if cannot get exact) received in most recently available year. Others include health insurance, external donors, church donations, NGOs etc.</i>	notes, Required															
30	s2q9_finc	9. Any other notes on the hospital financing and source of income. Has anything changed recently? Any changes expected in the upcoming years? What kinds of cost does specific sources have to cover? Who cover salary, building, equipment, drugs?	notes, Required															
31	s2q10_inc	10. Are any income streams only relevant for certain expenses (i.e. Donor X only funds ambulance costs, or Donor Y pays for drugs)	notes, Required															
32	s2q11_bal	11. How do you estimate the balance between the cost involved to run the maternity ward and the income it generates? <i>Does its income cover the costs, or is it subsidized by other services/income streams? This question might need to be rephrased to be more appropriate to context, as some hospitals, particularly faith-based, might not reveal this openly.</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>This question doesn't apply for us.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>The income generated exceeds the expenses</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>The income generated are about the same as the expenses</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>The income generated are less than the expenses</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Don't know/refused to answer</td> </tr> </table>	1	This question doesn't apply for us.	2	The income generated exceeds the expenses	3	The income generated are about the same as the expenses	4	The income generated are less than the expenses	5	Don't know/refused to answer					
1	This question doesn't apply for us.																	
2	The income generated exceeds the expenses																	
3	The income generated are about the same as the expenses																	
4	The income generated are less than the expenses																	
5	Don't know/refused to answer																	
33	s2q11a_bal	11a. If the previous answer does not apply to you, please explain why.	text															
34	s2q12_com	12. Comments on the above (was there any reluctance to provide this estimate, were additional people consulted in order to get it, etc)	text, Required															
35	s2q13_pay	13. To which extent the payment of health care providers is linked with the number of services they provide? (list all options and mark all that apply)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s2q13_pay__1</td> <td>Salary: they receive a fixed amount paid for a given period regardless of the number of services provided.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s2q13_pay__2</td> <td>Fee for service: they receive a separate payment for each service provided.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s2q13_pay__3</td> <td>Capitation/block payment: they are paid a "lump sum" per patient empaneled regardless of how many services the patient receives effectively</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>s2q13_pay__4</td> <td>Bundled payment in which providers are reimbursed on the basis of expected costs for clinically-defined episodes of care.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>s2q13_pay__5</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	s2q13_pay__1	Salary: they receive a fixed amount paid for a given period regardless of the number of services provided.	2	s2q13_pay__2	Fee for service: they receive a separate payment for each service provided.	3	s2q13_pay__3	Capitation/block payment: they are paid a "lump sum" per patient empaneled regardless of how many services the patient receives effectively	4	s2q13_pay__4	Bundled payment in which providers are reimbursed on the basis of expected costs for clinically-defined episodes of care.	5	s2q13_pay__5	Other
1	s2q13_pay__1	Salary: they receive a fixed amount paid for a given period regardless of the number of services provided.																
2	s2q13_pay__2	Fee for service: they receive a separate payment for each service provided.																
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4	s2q13_pay__4	Bundled payment in which providers are reimbursed on the basis of expected costs for clinically-defined episodes of care.																
5	s2q13_pay__5	Other																
36	s2q13a_payoth Show the field ONLY if: [s2q13_pay(5)]=1	13a. If you chose 'other' in the previous question, please specify	text, Required															
37	s2q14_prov	14. Comment on the answer to the question above: How does this payment works actually? Which type of payment applies for various kind of health workers ? <i>Models that mix two or models above for different kinds of staff and for different kinds of services are possible. Please describe them here. It is also possible that certain type of staff (midwives or gynecologists for instance) receive a certain type of payment while other receive other forms of payment. Please describe here.</i>	text, Required															
38	s2q15_staff	15. If there is a private ward in this hospital, are staff who work in the private wards paid differently? <i>(please note any comments or observations)</i>	text, Required															

39	s2q16_pay	16. Who pays the health care providers in this hospital?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s2q16_pay__1</td> <td>Hospital directly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s2q16_pay__2</td> <td>District government</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s2q16_pay__3</td> <td>MOH/central government</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>s2q16_pay__4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	s2q16_pay__1	Hospital directly	2	s2q16_pay__2	District government	3	s2q16_pay__3	MOH/central government	4	s2q16_pay__4	Other
1	s2q16_pay__1	Hospital directly													
2	s2q16_pay__2	District government													
3	s2q16_pay__3	MOH/central government													
4	s2q16_pay__4	Other													
40	s2q16a_payoth Show the field ONLY if: [s2q16_pay(4)]=1	16a. If you chose 'other' in the previous question please specify.	text, Required												
41	currency	What is the currency used for the cost related questions below (questions 17-25)?	text												
42	s2q17_ant	17. Do you charge official fees for antenatal care?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute (money, buy supplies, pay for ANC card etc)</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	2	No	3	No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute (money, buy supplies, pay for ANC card etc)						
1	Yes														
2	No														
3	No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute (money, buy supplies, pay for ANC card etc)														
43	s2q17a_ant Show the field ONLY if: [s2q17_ant]=1	17a. Please provide the extra fees charged for antenatal care	text (number)												
44	s2q18_ant	18. Comments on antenatal payment schemes	text, Required												
45	s2q19_vag	19. Do you charge fees for vaginal (normal) delivery? <i>Please note if there are certain exemptions (for referred women, for poor women, etc)</i>	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute (money, buy supplies)</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	2	No	3	No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute (money, buy supplies)						
1	Yes														
2	No														
3	No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute (money, buy supplies)														
46	s2q19a_vag Show the field ONLY if: [s2q19_vag]=1	Please provide the extra fees charged for vaginal (normal) delivery	text (number), Required												
47	s2q19b_vag Show the field ONLY if: [s2q19_vag]=3	Please provide an estimate of the amount/items you're asked to contribute	text (number), Required												
48	s2q20_norm	20. Comments on normal delivery payment (public versus private, other notes) <i>Please note if there are certain exemptions (for referred women, for poor women, etc)</i>	text, Required												
49	s2q21_kit	21. Do women need to buy a delivery pack/kit or are they expected to bring it with them?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	2	No	3	Other						
1	Yes														
2	No														
3	Other														
50	s2q21_kithoth Show the field ONLY if: [s2q21_kit]=3	21a. If you chose 'other' in the previous question, please specify	text												
51	s2q21b_kit Show the field ONLY if: [s2q21_kit]=1	21b. Please provide the estimated cost/ amount of delivery pack/kit	text (number), Required												
52	s2q22_cesa	22. Do you charge fees for c-sections?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	2	No	3	No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute						
1	Yes														
2	No														
3	No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute														

53	s2q22a_cesa Show the field ONLY if: [s2q22_cesa]=1	22a. Please provide the fees charged for c-sections	text (number), Required								
54	s2q22b_cesa Show the field ONLY if: [s2q22_cesa]=3	22b. Please provide an estimate of the amount/items that women asked to contribute	text (number), Required								
55	s2q23_pay	23. Comments on c-section delivery payment (public versus private, other notes) <i>Note if fees differ between elective and emergency c-section. Please note if there are certain exemptions (for referred women, for poor women, etc)</i>	text, Required								
56	s2q24_blo	24. Do you charge fees for blood transfusions?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No but families are asked to donate blood to replace stock</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	2	No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute	3	No but families are asked to donate blood to replace stock	4	Other
1	Yes										
2	No, but women sometimes are asked to contribute										
3	No but families are asked to donate blood to replace stock										
4	Other										
57	s2q24a_blo Show the field ONLY if: [s2q24_blo]=2 or [s2q24_blo]=3	24a. Please provide approximate amount or items	text (number), Required								
58	s2q24_blooth Show the field ONLY if: [s2q24_blo]=4	24b. If you chose 'other' to the previous question, please specify:	text, Required								
59	s2q25_tran	25. If there is a charge for transfusions, please note the amount per units	text (number), Required								
60	s2q26_oth	26. Can you tell me more about other payments that women are expected to pay during their stay in this hospital during and after childbirth, for example for postnatal care, newborn care (especially if admitted to NICU), anaesthesia, pain relief).	text, Required								
61	s2q27_agg	27. Regarding the provision of maternity care, does the hospital capture, aggregate and analyze any indicator/data above and beyond what is required by the national HMIS/DHIS2?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Not sure/I don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	Not sure/I don't know		
1	Yes										
0	No										
2	Not sure/I don't know										
62	s2q28_sour Show the field ONLY if: [s2q27_agg]=1	28. Notes on data and sources of the data that are captured beyond HMIS/DHIS2.	text, Required								
63	s2q29_covid	29. Was there any change in the general governance of the hospital due to COVID-19? Please describe what have changed. Probe only if necessary with the following questions (adapt them if necessary to the first round of answers provided by the respondent) - Possible changes may relate to appointment of a COVID19 response focal person in the administration in general and/or, in each ward, with or without changes in the lines of command. Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe. - It can be also the creation of new governance meetings/platforms/collaboratives to easy decision making around COVID19. Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe. - It is also possible that the interactions with the higher-level authorities get more frequent, in terms of visits, numbers of reporting etc. Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe. - It is possible that the financing usual procedures in the hospital get changed. Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe.	notes, Required								

64	hfa_section_2_general_hospital_governance_and_finance_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>Incomplete</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Unverified</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Complete</td></tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete												
0	Incomplete																				
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Instrument: Hfa Section 3 Basic Infrastructure And Supplies (hfa_section_3_basic_infrastructure_and_supplies)			^ Collapse																		
65	s3q1_nam	Section Header: <i>SECTION 3. Basic infrastructure and supplies: Hospital level</i> 1. Main respondent name	text, Required																		
66	s3q2_tit	2. Respondent title	text, Required																		
67	s3q3_oth	3. Was there anyone else in the meeting/tour? Provide name(s) and position(s)	text																		
68	s3q4_elec	4. What is the source of electricity in the hospital (mark all that apply):	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s3q4_elec__1</td><td>Network</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s3q4_elec__2</td><td>Generator</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s3q4_elec__3</td><td>Solar panels</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s3q4_elec__4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	s3q4_elec__1	Network	2	s3q4_elec__2	Generator	3	s3q4_elec__3	Solar panels	4	s3q4_elec__4	Other						
1	s3q4_elec__1	Network																			
2	s3q4_elec__2	Generator																			
3	s3q4_elec__3	Solar panels																			
4	s3q4_elec__4	Other																			
69	s3q4a_elecother Show the field ONLY if: [s3q4_elec(4)]=1	4a. If you chose other to the previous question, please specify	text, Required																		
70	s3q5_bac	5. Is there a backup power supply for refrigerators?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>I Don't know</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	I Don't know												
1	Yes																				
0	No																				
2	I Don't know																				
71	s3q5a_baccomm	5a. Are there additional comments on the previous question?	notes																		
72	s3q6_wat	6. What is the main source of water for the hospital? (mark all that apply):	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s3q6_wat__1</td><td>Piped water from network</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s3q6_wat__2</td><td>Water brought in tanker trucks or containers</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s3q6_wat__3</td><td>Borehole</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s3q6_wat__4</td><td>Well</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s3q6_wat__5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	s3q6_wat__1	Piped water from network	2	s3q6_wat__2	Water brought in tanker trucks or containers	3	s3q6_wat__3	Borehole	4	s3q6_wat__4	Well	5	s3q6_wat__5	Other			
1	s3q6_wat__1	Piped water from network																			
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4	s3q6_wat__4	Well																			
5	s3q6_wat__5	Other																			
73	s3q6a_watoth Show the field ONLY if: [s3q6_wat(5)]=1	6a. If you chose 'other' for the previous question, please specify:	text																		
74	s3q7_trea	7. Which method is used for the treatment of water at the hospital? (mark all that apply):	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s3q7_trea__1</td><td>No treatment at hospital</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s3q7_trea__2</td><td>Chlorination</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s3q7_trea__3</td><td>Filtration</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s3q7_trea__4</td><td>Boiling</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s3q7_trea__5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	s3q7_trea__1	No treatment at hospital	2	s3q7_trea__2	Chlorination	3	s3q7_trea__3	Filtration	4	s3q7_trea__4	Boiling	5	s3q7_trea__5	Other			
1	s3q7_trea__1	No treatment at hospital																			
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3	s3q7_trea__3	Filtration																			
4	s3q7_trea__4	Boiling																			
5	s3q7_trea__5	Other																			
75	s3q7a_treaoth Show the field ONLY if: [s3q7_trea(5)]=1	7a. If you chose 'other' for the previous question, please specify:	text																		
76	s3q8_wast	8. How is contaminated waste from this hospital usually treated? (mark all that apply):	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s3q8_wast__1</td><td>Off-site disposal</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s3q8_wast__2</td><td>Burning in an open pit</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s3q8_wast__3</td><td>Burial in a waste pit</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s3q8_wast__4</td><td>Disposal in landfill</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s3q8_wast__5</td><td>Incineration</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s3q8_wast__6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	s3q8_wast__1	Off-site disposal	2	s3q8_wast__2	Burning in an open pit	3	s3q8_wast__3	Burial in a waste pit	4	s3q8_wast__4	Disposal in landfill	5	s3q8_wast__5	Incineration	6	s3q8_wast__6	Other
1	s3q8_wast__1	Off-site disposal																			
2	s3q8_wast__2	Burning in an open pit																			
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5	s3q8_wast__5	Incineration																			
6	s3q8_wast__6	Other																			

77	s3q8a_wastoth Show the field ONLY if: [s3q8_wast(6)]=1	8a. If you chose 'other' for the previous question, please specify:	text																		
78	s3q9_tel	9. Does the hospital have a telephone or radio? (mark all that apply)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s3q9_tel__1</td> <td>Yes, landline</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s3q9_tel__2</td> <td>Yes, mobile</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s3q9_tel__3</td> <td>Yes, radio (VHF)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>s3q9_tel__4</td> <td>Yes, Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>s3q9_tel__0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	s3q9_tel__1	Yes, landline	2	s3q9_tel__2	Yes, mobile	3	s3q9_tel__3	Yes, radio (VHF)	4	s3q9_tel__4	Yes, Other	0	s3q9_tel__0	No			
1	s3q9_tel__1	Yes, landline																			
2	s3q9_tel__2	Yes, mobile																			
3	s3q9_tel__3	Yes, radio (VHF)																			
4	s3q9_tel__4	Yes, Other																			
0	s3q9_tel__0	No																			
79	s3q9a_teloht Show the field ONLY if: [s3q9_tel(4)]=1	9a. If you chose 'other' for the previous question, please specify:	text																		
80	s3q10_who	10. If the hospital has a mobile telephone who has it? Who charges it? comment	text, Required																		
81	s3q11_amb	11. Is the hospital served by a functioning ambulance? (mark all that apply)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s3q11_amb__1</td> <td>Yes - run by hospital</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s3q11_amb__2</td> <td>Yes - run by district authority</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s3q11_amb__3</td> <td>Yes, run by other nearby facilities</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>s3q11_amb__4</td> <td>Yes, private operator</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>s3q11_amb__5</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>s3q11_amb__0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	s3q11_amb__1	Yes - run by hospital	2	s3q11_amb__2	Yes - run by district authority	3	s3q11_amb__3	Yes, run by other nearby facilities	4	s3q11_amb__4	Yes, private operator	5	s3q11_amb__5	Other	0	s3q11_amb__0	No
1	s3q11_amb__1	Yes - run by hospital																			
2	s3q11_amb__2	Yes - run by district authority																			
3	s3q11_amb__3	Yes, run by other nearby facilities																			
4	s3q11_amb__4	Yes, private operator																			
5	s3q11_amb__5	Other																			
0	s3q11_amb__0	No																			
82	s3q11a_ambboth Show the field ONLY if: [s3q11_amb(5)]	11a. If you chose 'other' for the previous question please specify:	text, Required																		
83	s3q12_dri Show the field ONLY if: [s3q11_amb(1)]= 1 or [s3q11_amb(2)]= 2 or [s3q11_amb(3)]=3 or [s3q11_amb(4)]=4 or [s3q11_amb(5)]=5	12. If there is an ambulance operated by hospital, is there a driver for the ambulance present on the day of the visit?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																				
0	No																				
84	s3q13_fue Show the field ONLY if: [s3q11_amb(1)]= 1 or [s3q11_amb(2)]= 1 or [s3q11_amb(3)]=1 or [s3q11_amb(4)]=1 or [s3q11_amb(5)]=1	13. If there is an ambulance operated by hospital, does the ambulance have fuel on the day of the visit?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																				
0	No																				
85	s3q14_ref Show the field ONLY if: [s3q11_amb(1)]= 1 or [s3q11_amb(2)]= 1 or [s3q11_amb(3)]=1 or [s3q11_amb(4)]=1 or [s3q11_amb(5)]=1	14. If there is an ambulance operated by hospital, how many obstetric referrals did the hospital ambulance transport to the hospital in the last calendar month?	text (number), Required																		
86	s3q15_prev	15. What is your system of planned preventive maintenance and procurement in general?	text, Required																		
87	s3q16_covid	16. Were there any changes in basic infrastructure and supplies at hospital level to adapt to COVID-19? Please describe what have been done. Possible changes may relate to buying of a new ambulance or to the creation of a new call center or phone line, or investment in telemedicine capacities to adapt to COVID 19? Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe.	notes																		
88	hfa_section_3_basic_infrastructure_and_supplies_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete												
0	Incomplete																				
1	Unverified																				
2	Complete																				

Instrument: HFA Section 4: Basic Infrastructure For Maternal And Newborn Section (hfa_section_4_basic_infrastructure_for_maternal_an) ^ Collapse							
89	s4q1_nam	1. Respondent name	text, Required				
90	s4q2_tit	2. Respondent title	text, Required				
91	s4q3_oth	3. Was there anyone else in the meeting? Provide name(s) and position(s)	text				
92	s4q4_roo	4. Number of labour rooms	text (number), Required				
93	s4q5_1st	5. Number of beds for 1st stage of labour	text (number), Required				
94	s4q6_del	6. Number of delivery rooms	text (number), Required				
95	s4q7_2nd	7. Number of beds for 2nd stage of labour	text (number), Required				
96	s4q8_the	8. Is there a dedicated theatre to perform caesarean sections?	yesno, Required <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
97	s4q9_ope Show the field ONLY if: [s4q8_the]=1	9. Is the operating theatre part of the maternity area?	yesno, Required <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
98	s4q10_icu	10. Is there an Intensive Care Unit (ICU) which can admit women with obstetric complications? <i>ICU defined as a clinical area where ventilatory support can be provided</i>	yesno, Required <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table> Field Annotation: ICU defined as a clinical area where ventilatory support can be provided	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
99	s4q11_occu	11. Is there an Obstetric Critical Care Unit (OCCU)/ High Dependency Unit (HDU) for women with obstetric complications? <i>Operation definition of OCCU/HDU is "a clinical area with an enhanced nursing ratio of at least 1 staff per 4 patients where fluid balance, drug administration and continuous vital signs monitoring can be done"</i>	yesno, Required <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table> Field Annotation: Operation definition of OCCU/HDU is "a clinical area with an enhanced nursing ratio of at least 1 staff per 4 patients where fluid balance, drug administration and continuous vital signs monitoring can be done"	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
100	s4q12_tran Show the field ONLY if: [s4q11_occu]=0	12. If no, where are women in need of high or intensive care transferred?	text, Required				
101	s4q13_ecl	13. Is there an eclampsia room?	yesno, Required <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
102	s4q14_car Show the field ONLY if: [s4q13_ecl]=1	14. If yes, define what care is provided in the eclampsia room.	text, Required				
103	s4q15_new	15. Is there a room for sick newborns?	yesno, Required <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
104	s4q16_cot Show the field ONLY if: [s4q15_new]=1	16. If yes, what is the number of cots?	text, Required				
105	s4q17_nicu	17. Is there a neonatal intensive care unit (NICU)?	yesno, Required <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
106	s4q18_inc Show the field ONLY if: [s4q17_nicu]=1	18. If yes, what is the number of incubators?	text (number), Required				

107	s4q19_oxy	19. Is oxygen from cylinder available to sick newborns?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
108	s4q20_func Show the field ONLY if: [s4q19_oxy]=1	20. If yes, how many are functioning on day of visit	text (number), Required				
109	s4q21_pip	21. Is oxygen from piped gas supply available to sick newborns?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
110	s4q22_fun Show the field ONLY if: [s4q21_pip]=1	22. If yes, how many are functioning on day of visit	text (number)				
111	s4q23_con	23. Is oxygen from oxygen concentrator available to sick newborns?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
112	s4q24_fun Show the field ONLY if: [s4q23_con]=1	24. If yes, how many are functioning on day of visit	text (number), Required				
113	s4q25_vent	25. Is oxygen from Continuous Positive Airway Pressure (CPAP) ventilation available to sick newborns?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
114	s4q26_func Show the field ONLY if: [s4q25_vent]=1	26. If yes, how many are functioning on day of visit	text (number), Required				
115	s4q27_pul	27. Is pulse oximetry available to sick newborns?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
116	s4q28_moth	28. Can you tell me where the mothers of sick babies stay?	text, Required				
117	s4q29_kang	29. Is there a Kangaroo Mother Care program for preterm but healthy infants?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
118	s4q30_ant	30. Does this hospital offer routine antenatal care?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
119	s4q31_cons Show the field ONLY if: [s4q30_ant]=1	31. If yes, what is the number of antenatal consultations? Note calendar period (per month or year)	text, Required				
120	s4q32_comp	32. Can you tell me more about routine antenatal care and the antenatal care provided to complicated cases or referrals?	text, Required				
121	s4q33_out	33. Does this hospital offer routine outpatient postnatal care? Is it available for all women who gave birth in this hospital?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
122	s4q34_post Show the field ONLY if: [s4q33_out]=1	34. If yes, what is the number of routine outpatient postnatal consultations? Note calendar period (per month or year)	text (number), Required				
123	s4q35_priv	35. Does the hospital provide private maternity care?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						

124	s4q36_cas Show the field ONLY if: [s4q35_priv]=1	36. Approximately how many private maternity/delivery cases did you have in 2019?	text (number), Required															
125	s4q37_mat Show the field ONLY if: [s4q35_priv]=1	37. Can you tell me more about the private maternity care? Where do women deliver? Where do they receive postnatal care? What are the fees charged? <i>Note any key differences such as privacy, space, companion possibility, etc.</i>	text, Required Field Annotation: If have private maternity care. Note any key differences such as privacy, space, companion possibility, etc.															
126	hfa_section_4_basic_infrastru cture_for_maternal_an_compl ete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete									
0	Incomplete																	
1	Unverified																	
2	Complete																	
Instrument: Hfa Section 5 Basic Infrastructure And Supplies (hfa_section_5_basic_infrastructure_and_supplies)			^ Collapse															
127	s5q1_nam	Section Header: <i>SECTION 5. Basic infrastructure and supplies: Maternity ward level</i> 1. Main respondent name	text, Required															
128	s5q2_tit	2. Respondent title	text, Required															
129	s5q3_oth	3. Was there anyone else in the meeting/tour? Provide name(s) and position(s)	text, Required															
130	s5q4_pow	4. Has the maternity ward experienced electrical power outage in the last 7 days?	radio <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	Don't know									
1	Yes																	
0	No																	
2	Don't know																	
131	s5q5_wat	5. What is the most commonly used source of water for maternity ward and delivery area?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s5q5_wat__1</td> <td>Piped water from network</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s5q5_wat__2</td> <td>Water brought in tanker trucks or containers</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s5q5_wat__3</td> <td>Borehole</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>s5q5_wat__4</td> <td>Well</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>s5q5_wat__5</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	s5q5_wat__1	Piped water from network	2	s5q5_wat__2	Water brought in tanker trucks or containers	3	s5q5_wat__3	Borehole	4	s5q5_wat__4	Well	5	s5q5_wat__5	Other
1	s5q5_wat__1	Piped water from network																
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3	s5q5_wat__3	Borehole																
4	s5q5_wat__4	Well																
5	s5q5_wat__5	Other																
132	s5q5a_watoth Show the field ONLY if: [s5q5_wat(5)]=1	5a. If you chose 'other' in the previous question, please specify	text, Required															
133	s5q6_hour	6. Is running water available 24 hours in the maternity and delivery area?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No											
1	Yes																	
0	No																	
134	s5q7_shor	7. Has the maternity ward experienced shortage of running water in the last 7 days?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>I Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	I Don't know									
1	Yes																	
0	No																	
2	I Don't know																	
135	s5q7a_shor Show the field ONLY if: [s5q7_shor]=1	7a. Please indicate the number of days with shortage of running water	text (number), Required															
136	s5q8_cau Show the field ONLY if: [s5q7_shor]=1	8. If yes, what caused the interruption?	text, Required															

137	s5q9_tim	9. Are there times when there is a shortage of cleaning equipment/ products?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>No, never (cleaning products and equipment are always available)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Cleaning products are available but they are not always the recommended ones</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Cleaning products are not always available</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	No, never (cleaning products and equipment are always available)	2	Cleaning products are available but they are not always the recommended ones	3	Cleaning products are not always available	4	Other				
1	No, never (cleaning products and equipment are always available)														
2	Cleaning products are available but they are not always the recommended ones														
3	Cleaning products are not always available														
4	Other														
138	s5q9a_timoth Show the field ONLY if: [s5q9_tim]=4	9a. If you chose 'other' to the previous question, please specify	text												
139	s5q10_toil	10. What is the number of toilets/latrines in the maternity and delivery area functional for staff today?	text (number), Required												
140	s5q10a_toil	10. What is the number of toilets/latrines in the maternity and delivery area functional for patients today?	text (number), Required												
141	s5q11_clea	11. Is the cleaning of the following areas carried out routinely after delivery? (mark all that apply)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s5q11_clea__1</td> <td>Cleaning the equipment in delivery unit</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s5q11_clea__2</td> <td>Cleaning the linen</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s5q11_clea__3</td> <td>Cleaning the delivery Beds/Mattresses</td> </tr> </table>	1	s5q11_clea__1	Cleaning the equipment in delivery unit	2	s5q11_clea__2	Cleaning the linen	3	s5q11_clea__3	Cleaning the delivery Beds/Mattresses			
1	s5q11_clea__1	Cleaning the equipment in delivery unit													
2	s5q11_clea__2	Cleaning the linen													
3	s5q11_clea__3	Cleaning the delivery Beds/Mattresses													
142	s5q12_glo	12. What is the main type of gloves used in the delivery unit?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Re-usable (autoclaved)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Reusable (washes with water)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Reusable (washed in disinfectant)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Disposable gloves</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Re-usable (autoclaved)	2	Reusable (washes with water)	3	Reusable (washed in disinfectant)	4	Disposable gloves	5	Other		
1	Re-usable (autoclaved)														
2	Reusable (washes with water)														
3	Reusable (washed in disinfectant)														
4	Disposable gloves														
5	Other														
143	s5q12a_glooth Show the field ONLY if: [s5q12_glo]=5	12a. If you chose 'other' in the previous question, please specify	text												
144	s5q13_cont	13. Are specific containers available for disposing of needles and other sharps in the maternity area?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes														
0	No														
145	s5q14_wast	14. Is infectious waste stored separately from non-infectious waste in the maternity area?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes														
0	No														
146	s5q15_pla	15. Where do you dispose of the placentas? (mark all that apply)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s5q15_pla__1</td> <td>Pit</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s5q15_pla__2</td> <td>Incinerator</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s5q15_pla__3</td> <td>Given to patients</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>s5q15_pla__4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	s5q15_pla__1	Pit	2	s5q15_pla__2	Incinerator	3	s5q15_pla__3	Given to patients	4	s5q15_pla__4	Other
1	s5q15_pla__1	Pit													
2	s5q15_pla__2	Incinerator													
3	s5q15_pla__3	Given to patients													
4	s5q15_pla__4	Other													
147	s5q15_plaoth Show the field ONLY if: [s5q15_pla(4)]=1	If you chose 'other' in the previous question, please specify	text												
148	s5q16_tel	16. Does the maternity ward have a telephone line?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes, landline (dedicated number)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Yes, landline (extension within hospital)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Yes, dedicated mobile</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes, landline (dedicated number)	2	Yes, landline (extension within hospital)	3	Yes, dedicated mobile	0	No				
1	Yes, landline (dedicated number)														
2	Yes, landline (extension within hospital)														
3	Yes, dedicated mobile														
0	No														
149	s5q17_tra	17. What are the main modes of transport in which obstetric referrals reach the hospital? <i>If possible list approximate breakdown, for example: 50% - hospital ambulance 30% - private taxis</i>	text, Required												

150	s5q18_inf	18. How does the maternity ward receive information about incoming maternity referrals? <i>Who is notified, how, how recorded, what % of incoming referrals are notified in advance, where is the information noted - patient file? Register?</i>	text, Required																								
151	s5q19_ref	19. What is the transport system, women use to reach another hospital when they are referred by this hospital? Please describe how the system works in practice	text, Required																								
152	s5q20_faci	20. Which facilities are the main source of obstetric referrals to this hospital? <i>Try to get the main referring facility names, with number of cases per month, if possible.</i>	text, Required																								
153	s5q21_exc	21. How often does the number of women exceed the number of delivery beds?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every day or nearly every day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>About once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>About once a month</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Few times per year</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Never</td></tr> </table>	1	Every day or nearly every day	2	About once a week	3	About once a month	4	Few times per year	5	Never														
1	Every day or nearly every day																										
2	About once a week																										
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4	Few times per year																										
5	Never																										
154	s5q22_cap	22. What happens in the maternity ward when usual bed capacity is exceeded? (mark all that apply) <i>Comment on what the occupancy looked like on the day of the visit</i>	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s5q22_cap__1</td><td>Additional beds are added to the ward</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s5q22_cap__2</td><td>Women are placed in another ward</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s5q22_cap__3</td><td>Women are placed in beds in corridor</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s5q22_cap__4</td><td>Women are placed on the floor</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s5q22_cap__5</td><td>More than one woman is placed on each bed</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s5q22_cap__6</td><td>Women are discharged early</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s5q22_cap__7</td><td>Women are turned away/referred out</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s5q22_cap__8</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	s5q22_cap__1	Additional beds are added to the ward	2	s5q22_cap__2	Women are placed in another ward	3	s5q22_cap__3	Women are placed in beds in corridor	4	s5q22_cap__4	Women are placed on the floor	5	s5q22_cap__5	More than one woman is placed on each bed	6	s5q22_cap__6	Women are discharged early	7	s5q22_cap__7	Women are turned away/referred out	8	s5q22_cap__8	Other
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7	s5q22_cap__7	Women are turned away/referred out																									
8	s5q22_cap__8	Other																									
155	s5q22a_capoth	22a. If you chose 'other' in the previous question, please specify	text																								
156	s5q23_covid	23. Were there any changes in basic infrastructure for maternal and newborn section to adapt due to COVID-19? Please describe what have been done. Possible changes may relate to the identification of a triage place for COVID19 with appropriate equipment or to the setting of a specific room for pregnant women with COVID19 to adapt to COVID 19? Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe.	text, Required																								
157	hfa_section_5_basic_infrastructure_and_supplies_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>Incomplete</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Unverified</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Complete</td></tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete																		
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2	Complete																										
Instrument: Hfa Section 6 Basic Infrastructure And Supplies Observation (hfa_section_6_basic_infrastructure_and_supplies_observation) ^ Collapse																											
158	s6q1_ele	Section Header: <i>SECTION 6. Basic infrastructure and supplies: Observation checklist maternity ward</i> 1. Is there electricity in the maternity ward at the time of visit?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes, enough</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Yes, but not enough</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes, enough	2	Yes, but not enough	0	No																		
1	Yes, enough																										
2	Yes, but not enough																										
0	No																										
159	s6q2_wash	Section Header: <i>Hand washing- admission area of maternity ward</i> 2. Is there a hand washing station? with running water?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes, enough</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Yes, but not enough</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes, enough	2	Yes, but not enough	0	No																		
1	Yes, enough																										
2	Yes, but not enough																										
0	No																										

160	s6q3_wat	3. Running water?	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
161	s6q4_soap	4. Soap or suitable alternative for hand washing available? (hand disinfectant?)	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
162	s6q5_stat	Section Header: <i>Hand washing- the delivery beds of the maternity ward</i> 5. Is there a hand washing station? with running water? the delivery beds of the maternity ward	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
163	s6q6_wat	6. Running water? - the delivery beds of the maternity ward	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
164	s6q7_soap	7. Soap or suitable alternative for hand washing available? (hand disinfectant?) - the delivery beds of the maternity ward	radio 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
165	s6q8_rub	Section Header: <i>Hand rub- delivery area/beds</i> 8. Is alcohol-based hand rub available for hand hygiene in the delivery area?	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
166	s6q9_alc	Section Header: <i>Hand rub- c-section theatre</i> 9. Is alcohol-based hand rub available for hand hygiene in the c-section theatre?	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
167	s6q10_func	Section Header: <i>The patient toilet/latrine in the maternity/delivery area</i> 10. The patient toilet/latrine in the maternity/delivery is functional ?	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
168	s6q11_clea	11. Toilets are clean in the patient toilet/latrine in the maternity/delivery?	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
169	s6q12_sme	12. Toilets /latrine in the maternity/delivery do not smell	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
170	s6q13_hand	13. Hand washing station are available in or near the patient toilet/latrine in the maternity/delivery area	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
171	s6q14_soap	14. Soap or suitable alternative for hand washing are available in or near the patient toilet/latrine in the maternity/delivery area	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No

172	s6q15_wat	15. Water available for hand washing in or near the patient toilet/latrine in the maternity/delivery area?	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
173	s6q16_clea	16. Clean water for hand washing available in or near the patient toilet/latrine in the maternity/delivery area ?	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
174	s6q17_bin	17. Bins for pads and other solid waste are available in or near the patient toilet/latrine in the maternity/delivery area?	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
175	s6q18_mat	18. Materials for anal cleansing (water+receptacle; toilet paper) are available in or near the patient toilet/latrine in the maternity/delivery area?	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
176	s6q19_clea	19. The delivery bed mattresses are visibly clean	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
177	s6q20_int	20. The delivery bed mattresses are cover intact, free from signs of damage, rips or cracks?	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
178	s6q21_easy	21. The delivery bed mattresses are covered with an easily cleanable, waterproof material	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
179	s6q22_staf	22. Drinking water (i.e. potable water) in the maternity ward is available for staff.	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
180	s6q23_pat	23. Drinking water (i.e. potable water) in the maternity ward is available for patients.	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
181	s6q24_avai	24. Surgical gloves in the delivery areas are available.	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
182	s6q25_cont	25. Surgical gloves in the delivery areas are stored away from contamination risk (stored in a box or container)	radio 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
183	s6q26_clo	26. Surgical gloves in the delivery areas are close to the point of care	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No

184	s6q27_sink	27. Posters displaying prompts to wash hands are above sinks in maternity area	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
185	s6q28_sink	28. Posters displaying prompts to wash hands are above sinks in delivery unit	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
186	s6q29_toil	29. Posters displaying prompts to wash hands are above sinks in the latrines/toilets	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
187	s6q30_toil	30. Posters displaying prompts to wash hands are in the latrines/toilets	radio, Required 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
188	s6q31_mask	31. Are there face masks (simple cloth masks) available for the staff?	radio 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
189	s6q32_ffp23	32. Are there higher-level protection masks (FFP 2 or 3 or equivalent)?	radio 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
190	s6q33_visors	33. Are there visors/face shields?	radio 1 Yes, enough 2 Yes, but not enough 0 No
191	s6q34_clean	34. Has the frequency of routine cleaning of the maternity ward changed during the past month as compared to the beginning of the COVID-19 outbreak?	radio 0 Yes increased 1 Yes, decreased 2 Unchanged since the outbreak began 3 Not applicable 4 Don't know
192	hfa_section_6_basic_infrastru cture_and_supplies_observati on_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown 0 Incomplete 1 Unverified 2 Complete
Instrument: Hfa Section 7 Key Statistics For Maternal And Newborn Section (hfa_section_7_key_statistics_for_maternal_and_newb) ^ Collapse			
193	s7q1_nam	Section Header: <i>SECTION 7. Key statistics for maternal and newborn section</i> 1. Respondent name	text, Required
194	s7q2_tit	2. Respondent title	text, Required
195	s7q3_oth	3. Was there anyone else in the meeting? Provide name(s) and position(s)	text
196	s7q4_stat	4. Any comments and notes on how statistics on referral are kept	text

197	s7q5_data	5. Can you tell me about the sources of data where neonatal deaths are recorded? (in maternity ward and neonatal ward separately?)	text						
198	s7q6_rev	6. Can I take a copy of the Maternal Death review form?	descriptive						
199	s7q7_hos	7. Average length of hospitalization after vaginal birth Please describe the timing of discharge for a woman with a vaginal singleton birth without any complications. (Prompt: when do the discharge rounds take place? Is everyone discharged at the same time every day? Etc) Prompt: If a woman gives birth vaginally without complications at 8am, when would she normally be discharged? How about if she delivers at 6pm?	text						
200	s7q8_tim	8. Average length of hospitalization after caesarean birth Please describe the timing of discharge for a woman with an emergency C-section birth. How many days would she usually stay?	text						
201	hfa_section_7_key_statistics_for_maternal_and_newborn_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete
0	Incomplete								
1	Unverified								
2	Complete								

Instrument: **HFA Section 8: Understanding Of Labour Companionship** (hfa_section_8_understanding_of_labour_companionship) [^ Collapse](#)

202	s8q1_nam	1. Respondent name	text, Required				
203	s8q2_tit	2. Respondent title	text, Required				
204	s8q3_oth	3. Was there anyone else in the meeting? Provide name(s) and position(s)?	text				
205	s8q4_all	4. Description of who is currently allowed to act as a companion for the woman? <i>Include issues such as do they have to be a family member, a female, etc?</i>	text, Required				
206	s8q5_tim	5. Description of for what periods of time companionship is offered (e.g.: from admission to discharge, during labour but not childbirth, only at childbirth)	text, Required				
207	s8q7_first	Section Header: <i>Please detail at what stages/and time of the day are companions allowed:</i> 7. Were companions allowed during Labour / first stage?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
208	s8q8_sec	8. Were companions allowed during Delivery / second stage?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
209	s8q9_imm	9. Were companions allowed during immediate postpartum period (first hour or two)?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
210	s8q10_post	10. Were companions allowed during postnatal ward?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
211	s8q11_day	11. Were companions allowed during Day-time?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
212	s8q12_night	12. Were companions allowed during Night-time?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
213	s8q13_rol	13. Description of the roles that companions usually undertake (e.g.: emotional support, providing food/water/tea to the woman, supporting staff)	text, Required				
214	s8q14_int	14. Description of how staff currently interact with companions	text, Required				

215	s8q15_orien	15. Existence and content of any orientation materials, protocols, or guidelines related to how staff should work with companions, or on the role of companions. If material exist take a copy. If no materials exist, please state this.	text, Required						
216	s8q16_feed	16. Any other feedback, observations or reflections <i>For example, are companions included in antenatal care/counselling?</i>	notes						
217	s8q17_covid19	17. Were there any changes in visitors, hospitalization companionship, and birth companionship policy in the hospital to adapt due to COVID-19? Please describe what have been done. Possible changes may relate to the denial/or limitation of access to the facility or to the maternity for visitor to adapt to COVID 19, suppression or limitation of the birth companionship to adapt to COVID19, visitors to women in postnatal ward or visitors to NICU (incl mother)? Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe.	notes						
218	hfa_section_8_understanding_of_labour_companionship_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete
0	Incomplete								
1	Unverified								
2	Complete								

Instrument: **HFA Section 9: Perinatal Health Care Human Resource in the Maternity****Ward** (hfa_section_9_perinatal_health_care_human_resource)[^ Collapse](#)

219	s9q1_obs	Section Header: <i>SECTION 9. Perinatal health care - human resources in the maternity ward</i> 1. Please indicate total number of obstetricians	text (number)																																																
220	s9q1a_obs Show the field ONLY if: [s9q1_obs]>=1	1a. Training received in last 2 years by Obstetricians	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__1</td> <td>EmONC</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__2</td> <td>EmONC - making it happen</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__3</td> <td>Lifesaving skills</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__4</td> <td>ALSO</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__5</td> <td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__6</td> <td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__7</td> <td>Essential care for labour and birth</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__8</td> <td>Helping babies survive</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__9</td> <td>Care for premature babies</td> </tr> <tr> <td>10</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__10</td> <td>AMTSL</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__11</td> <td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td> </tr> <tr> <td>12</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__12</td> <td>Antenatal care</td> </tr> <tr> <td>13</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__13</td> <td>Postnatal care</td> </tr> <tr> <td>14</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__14</td> <td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td> </tr> <tr> <td>15</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__15</td> <td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td> </tr> <tr> <td>16</td> <td>s9q1a_obs__16</td> <td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td> </tr> </table>	1	s9q1a_obs__1	EmONC	2	s9q1a_obs__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q1a_obs__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q1a_obs__4	ALSO	5	s9q1a_obs__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q1a_obs__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q1a_obs__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q1a_obs__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q1a_obs__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q1a_obs__10	AMTSL	11	s9q1a_obs__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q1a_obs__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q1a_obs__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q1a_obs__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q1a_obs__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q1a_obs__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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221	s9q2_neo	2. Please indicate total number of neonatologists	text (number)																																																

222	s9q2a_neo Show the field ONLY if: [s9q2_neo]>=1	2a. Training received in last 2 years by Neonatologists	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q2a_neo__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q2a_neo__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q2a_neo__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q2a_neo__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q2a_neo__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q2a_neo__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q2a_neo__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q2a_neo__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q2a_neo__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q2a_neo__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q2a_neo__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q2a_neo__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q2a_neo__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q2a_neo__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q2a_neo__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q2a_neo__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q2a_neo__1	EmONC	2	s9q2a_neo__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q2a_neo__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q2a_neo__4	ALSO	5	s9q2a_neo__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q2a_neo__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q2a_neo__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q2a_neo__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q2a_neo__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q2a_neo__10	AMTSL	11	s9q2a_neo__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q2a_neo__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q2a_neo__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q2a_neo__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q2a_neo__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q2a_neo__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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223	s9q3_pae	3. Please indicate total number of paediatricians	text (number)																																																
224	s9q3a_pae Show the field ONLY if: [s9q3_pae]>=1	3a. Training received in last 2 years by Paediatricians	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q3a_pae__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q3a_pae__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q3a_pae__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q3a_pae__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q3a_pae__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q3a_pae__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q3a_pae__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q3a_pae__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q3a_pae__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q3a_pae__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q3a_pae__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q3a_pae__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q3a_pae__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q3a_pae__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q3a_pae__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q3a_pae__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q3a_pae__1	EmONC	2	s9q3a_pae__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q3a_pae__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q3a_pae__4	ALSO	5	s9q3a_pae__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q3a_pae__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q3a_pae__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q3a_pae__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q3a_pae__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q3a_pae__10	AMTSL	11	s9q3a_pae__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q3a_pae__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q3a_pae__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q3a_pae__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q3a_pae__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q3a_pae__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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226	s9q4a_anae Show the field ONLY if: [s9q4_anae]>=1	4a. Training received in last 2 years by Anaesthesiologists	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q4a_anae__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q4a_anae__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q4a_anae__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q4a_anae__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q4a_anae__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q4a_anae__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q4a_anae__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q4a_anae__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q4a_anae__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q4a_anae__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q4a_anae__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q4a_anae__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q4a_anae__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q4a_anae__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q4a_anae__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q4a_anae__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q4a_anae__1	EmONC	2	s9q4a_anae__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q4a_anae__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q4a_anae__4	ALSO	5	s9q4a_anae__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q4a_anae__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q4a_anae__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q4a_anae__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q4a_anae__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q4a_anae__10	AMTSL	11	s9q4a_anae__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q4a_anae__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q4a_anae__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q4a_anae__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q4a_anae__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q4a_anae__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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228	s9q5a_spec Show the field ONLY if: [s9q5_spec]>=1	5a. Training received in last 2 years - Specialist in training: Obstetric	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q5a_spec__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q5a_spec__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q5a_spec__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q5a_spec__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q5a_spec__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q5a_spec__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q5a_spec__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q5a_spec__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q5a_spec__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q5a_spec__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q5a_spec__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q5a_spec__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q5a_spec__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q5a_spec__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q5a_spec__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q5a_spec__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q5a_spec__1	EmONC	2	s9q5a_spec__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q5a_spec__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q5a_spec__4	ALSO	5	s9q5a_spec__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q5a_spec__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q5a_spec__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q5a_spec__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q5a_spec__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q5a_spec__10	AMTSL	11	s9q5a_spec__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q5a_spec__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q5a_spec__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q5a_spec__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q5a_spec__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q5a_spec__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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230	s9q6a_med Show the field ONLY if: [s9q6_med]>=1	6a. Training received in last 2 years - Medical officer	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q6a_med__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q6a_med__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q6a_med__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q6a_med__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q6a_med__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q6a_med__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q6a_med__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q6a_med__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q6a_med__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q6a_med__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q6a_med__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q6a_med__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q6a_med__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q6a_med__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q6a_med__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q6a_med__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q6a_med__1	EmONC	2	s9q6a_med__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q6a_med__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q6a_med__4	ALSO	5	s9q6a_med__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q6a_med__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q6a_med__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q6a_med__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q6a_med__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q6a_med__10	AMTSL	11	s9q6a_med__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q6a_med__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q6a_med__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q6a_med__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q6a_med__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q6a_med__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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232	s9q7a_res Show the field ONLY if: [s9q7_res]>=1	7a. Training received in last 2 years - Residents (Medics in specialist training)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q7a_res__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q7a_res__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q7a_res__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q7a_res__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q7a_res__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q7a_res__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q7a_res__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q7a_res__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q7a_res__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q7a_res__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q7a_res__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q7a_res__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q7a_res__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q7a_res__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q7a_res__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q7a_res__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q7a_res__1	EmONC	2	s9q7a_res__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q7a_res__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q7a_res__4	ALSO	5	s9q7a_res__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q7a_res__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q7a_res__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q7a_res__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q7a_res__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q7a_res__10	AMTSL	11	s9q7a_res__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q7a_res__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q7a_res__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q7a_res__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q7a_res__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q7a_res__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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234	s9q8a_int Show the field ONLY if: [s9q8_int]>=1	8a. Training received in last 2 years - Intern medical officer (new MBBS graduate)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q8a_int__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q8a_int__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q8a_int__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q8a_int__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q8a_int__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q8a_int__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q8a_int__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q8a_int__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q8a_int__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q8a_int__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q8a_int__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q8a_int__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q8a_int__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q8a_int__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q8a_int__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q8a_int__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q8a_int__1	EmONC	2	s9q8a_int__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q8a_int__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q8a_int__4	ALSO	5	s9q8a_int__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q8a_int__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q8a_int__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q8a_int__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q8a_int__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q8a_int__10	AMTSL	11	s9q8a_int__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q8a_int__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q8a_int__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q8a_int__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q8a_int__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q8a_int__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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235	s9q9_ass	9. Please indicate total number of assistant medical officers	text (number)																																																
236	s9q9a_ass Show the field ONLY if: [s9q9_ass]>=1	9a. Training received in last 2 years - Assistant Medical officer	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q9a_ass__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q9a_ass__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q9a_ass__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q9a_ass__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q9a_ass__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q9a_ass__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q9a_ass__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q9a_ass__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q9a_ass__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q9a_ass__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q9a_ass__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q9a_ass__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q9a_ass__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q9a_ass__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q9a_ass__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q9a_ass__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q9a_ass__1	EmONC	2	s9q9a_ass__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q9a_ass__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q9a_ass__4	ALSO	5	s9q9a_ass__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q9a_ass__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q9a_ass__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q9a_ass__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q9a_ass__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q9a_ass__10	AMTSL	11	s9q9a_ass__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q9a_ass__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q9a_ass__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q9a_ass__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q9a_ass__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q9a_ass__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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239	s9q11_anes	11. Please indicate total number of anesthetist/anesthetic clinical officers	text (number)																																																
240	s9q11a_anes Show the field ONLY if: [s9q11_anes]>=1	11a. Training received in last 2 years - Anesthetist/anesthetic clinical officers	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q11a_anes__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q11a_anes__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q11a_anes__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q11a_anes__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q11a_anes__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q11a_anes__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q11a_anes__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q11a_anes__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q11a_anes__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q11a_anes__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q11a_anes__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q11a_anes__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q11a_anes__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q11a_anes__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q11a_anes__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q11a_anes__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q11a_anes__1	EmONC	2	s9q11a_anes__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q11a_anes__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q11a_anes__4	ALSO	5	s9q11a_anes__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q11a_anes__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q11a_anes__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q11a_anes__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q11a_anes__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q11a_anes__10	AMTSL	11	s9q11a_anes__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q11a_anes__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q11a_anes__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q11a_anes__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q11a_anes__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q11a_anes__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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241	s9q12_nur	12. Please indicate total number of nurses or nurse/midwives (registered)	text (number)																																																

242	s9q12a_nur Show the field ONLY if: [s9q12_nur]>=1	12a. Training received in last 2 years - Nurses or nurse/midwives) (registered)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q12a_nur__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q12a_nur__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q12a_nur__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q12a_nur__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q12a_nur__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q12a_nur__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q12a_nur__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q12a_nur__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q12a_nur__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q12a_nur__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q12a_nur__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q12a_nur__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q12a_nur__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q12a_nur__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q12a_nur__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q12a_nur__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q12a_nur__1	EmONC	2	s9q12a_nur__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q12a_nur__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q12a_nur__4	ALSO	5	s9q12a_nur__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q12a_nur__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q12a_nur__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q12a_nur__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q12a_nur__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q12a_nur__10	AMTSL	11	s9q12a_nur__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q12a_nur__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q12a_nur__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q12a_nur__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q12a_nur__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q12a_nur__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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244	s9q13a_reg Show the field ONLY if: [s9q13_reg]>=1	13a. Training received in last 2 years - Midwives (registered)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q13a_reg__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q13a_reg__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q13a_reg__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q13a_reg__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q13a_reg__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q13a_reg__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q13a_reg__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q13a_reg__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q13a_reg__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q13a_reg__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q13a_reg__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q13a_reg__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q13a_reg__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q13a_reg__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q13a_reg__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q13a_reg__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q13a_reg__1	EmONC	2	s9q13a_reg__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q13a_reg__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q13a_reg__4	ALSO	5	s9q13a_reg__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q13a_reg__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q13a_reg__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q13a_reg__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q13a_reg__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q13a_reg__10	AMTSL	11	s9q13a_reg__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q13a_reg__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q13a_reg__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q13a_reg__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q13a_reg__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q13a_reg__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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245	s9q14_enr	14. Please indicate total number of midwives (enrolled)	text (number)																																																

246	s9q14a_enr Show the field ONLY if: [s9q14_enr]>=1	14a. Training received in last 2 years - Midwives (enrolled)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q14a_enr__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q14a_enr__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q14a_enr__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q14a_enr__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q14a_enr__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q14a_enr__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q14a_enr__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q14a_enr__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q14a_enr__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q14a_enr__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q14a_enr__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q14a_enr__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q14a_enr__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q14a_enr__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q14a_enr__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q14a_enr__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q14a_enr__1	EmONC	2	s9q14a_enr__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q14a_enr__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q14a_enr__4	ALSO	5	s9q14a_enr__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q14a_enr__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q14a_enr__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q14a_enr__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q14a_enr__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q14a_enr__10	AMTSL	11	s9q14a_enr__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q14a_enr__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q14a_enr__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q14a_enr__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q14a_enr__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q14a_enr__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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247	s9q15_anae	15. Please indicate total number of nurse anesthetists	text (number)																																																
248	s9q15a_anae Show the field ONLY if: [s9q15_anae]>=1	15a. Training received in last 2 years - Nurse anesthetist	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q15a_anae__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q15a_anae__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q15a_anae__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q15a_anae__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q15a_anae__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q15a_anae__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q15a_anae__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q15a_anae__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q15a_anae__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q15a_anae__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q15a_anae__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q15a_anae__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q15a_anae__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q15a_anae__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q15a_anae__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q15a_anae__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q15a_anae__1	EmONC	2	s9q15a_anae__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q15a_anae__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q15a_anae__4	ALSO	5	s9q15a_anae__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q15a_anae__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q15a_anae__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q15a_anae__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q15a_anae__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q15a_anae__10	AMTSL	11	s9q15a_anae__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q15a_anae__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q15a_anae__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q15a_anae__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q15a_anae__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q15a_anae__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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249	s9q16_oth	16. Please indicate total number of other clinical staff	text (number)																																																

250	s9q16a_oth Show the field ONLY if: [s9q16_oth]>=1	16a. Training received in last 2 years - other_clinical_staff_specify	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q16a_oth__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q16a_oth__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q16a_oth__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q16a_oth__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q16a_oth__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q16a_oth__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q16a_oth__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q16a_oth__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q16a_oth__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q16a_oth__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q16a_oth__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q16a_oth__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q16a_oth__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q16a_oth__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q16a_oth__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q16a_oth__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q16a_oth__1	EmONC	2	s9q16a_oth__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q16a_oth__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q16a_oth__4	ALSO	5	s9q16a_oth__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q16a_oth__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q16a_oth__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q16a_oth__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q16a_oth__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q16a_oth__10	AMTSL	11	s9q16a_oth__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q16a_oth__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q16a_oth__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q16a_oth__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q16a_oth__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q16a_oth__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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251	s9q16b_oth	16b. Please specify the professional background of clinical staff	text																																																
252	s9q17_low	17. Please indicate total number of other nursing / midwifery staff (lower grade than enrolled)	text (number)																																																
253	s9q17b_low Show the field ONLY if: [s9q17_low]>=1	17a. Training received in last 2 years - Other nursing / midwifery staff (lower grade than enrolled)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q17b_low__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q17b_low__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q17b_low__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q17b_low__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q17b_low__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q17b_low__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q17b_low__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q17b_low__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q17b_low__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q17b_low__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q17b_low__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q17b_low__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q17b_low__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q17b_low__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q17b_low__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q17b_low__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q17b_low__1	EmONC	2	s9q17b_low__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q17b_low__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q17b_low__4	ALSO	5	s9q17b_low__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q17b_low__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q17b_low__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q17b_low__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q17b_low__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q17b_low__10	AMTSL	11	s9q17b_low__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q17b_low__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q17b_low__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q17b_low__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q17b_low__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q17b_low__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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255	s9q18a_ope Show the field ONLY if: [s9q18_ope]>=1	18a. Training received in last 2 years - Operating theatre nurses (where this role is not met by midwifery staff)	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q18a_ope__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q18a_ope__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q18a_ope__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q18a_ope__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q18a_ope__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q18a_ope__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q18a_ope__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q18a_ope__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q18a_ope__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q18a_ope__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q18a_ope__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q18a_ope__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q18a_ope__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q18a_ope__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q18a_ope__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q18a_ope__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q18a_ope__1	EmONC	2	s9q18a_ope__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q18a_ope__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q18a_ope__4	ALSO	5	s9q18a_ope__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q18a_ope__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q18a_ope__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q18a_ope__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q18a_ope__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q18a_ope__10	AMTSL	11	s9q18a_ope__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q18a_ope__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q18a_ope__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q18a_ope__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q18a_ope__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q18a_ope__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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257	s9q19a_clea Show the field ONLY if: [s9q19_clea]>=1	19a. Training received in last 2 years - Cleaning staff	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s9q19a_clea__1</td><td>EmONC</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s9q19a_clea__2</td><td>EmONC - making it happen</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s9q19a_clea__3</td><td>Lifesaving skills</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>s9q19a_clea__4</td><td>ALSO</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>s9q19a_clea__5</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - PPH</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>s9q19a_clea__6</td><td>Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>s9q19a_clea__7</td><td>Essential care for labour and birth</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>s9q19a_clea__8</td><td>Helping babies survive</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>s9q19a_clea__9</td><td>Care for premature babies</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>s9q19a_clea__10</td><td>AMTSL</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>s9q19a_clea__11</td><td>Maternal and newborn deaths reviews</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>s9q19a_clea__12</td><td>Antenatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>s9q19a_clea__13</td><td>Postnatal care</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>s9q19a_clea__14</td><td>Midwives Emergency Skills Training</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>s9q19a_clea__15</td><td>Early Essential Newborn Care</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>s9q19a_clea__16</td><td>PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants</td></tr> </table>	1	s9q19a_clea__1	EmONC	2	s9q19a_clea__2	EmONC - making it happen	3	s9q19a_clea__3	Lifesaving skills	4	s9q19a_clea__4	ALSO	5	s9q19a_clea__5	Helping Mothers Survive - PPH	6	s9q19a_clea__6	Helping Mothers Survive - Pre-eclampsia / Eclampsia	7	s9q19a_clea__7	Essential care for labour and birth	8	s9q19a_clea__8	Helping babies survive	9	s9q19a_clea__9	Care for premature babies	10	s9q19a_clea__10	AMTSL	11	s9q19a_clea__11	Maternal and newborn deaths reviews	12	s9q19a_clea__12	Antenatal care	13	s9q19a_clea__13	Postnatal care	14	s9q19a_clea__14	Midwives Emergency Skills Training	15	s9q19a_clea__15	Early Essential Newborn Care	16	s9q19a_clea__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants
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15	s9q19a_clea__15	Early Essential Newborn Care																																																	
16	s9q19a_clea__16	PMTCT/HIV care for mothers and infants																																																	
258	s9q20_rota	20. Is there a rota of cleaning duties to be performed by cleaners/nurses each day?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No																																												
1	Yes																																																		
0	No																																																		

259	s9q21_sup	21. Who supervises the performance of cleaners?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>- Head cleaner</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>- Ward nurses</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>- Administrative staff</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>- No supervision</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>- Other, specify: _____</td></tr> </table>	1	- Head cleaner	2	- Ward nurses	3	- Administrative staff	4	- No supervision	5	- Other, specify: _____
1	- Head cleaner												
2	- Ward nurses												
3	- Administrative staff												
4	- No supervision												
5	- Other, specify: _____												
260	s9q22_staf	22. Is there cleaning staff on duty at night?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes												
0	No												
261	s9q23_who	23. If no, who cleans at night?	text, Required										
262	s9q24_shift	24. Please specify professional cadres that are working on week days (Monday to Friday)	text										
263	s9q24a_shift	24a. Please provide number of cadre working on a day shift Monday to Friday	text (number)										
264	s9q24b_shift	24b. Please provide duration of a day shift (Monday to Friday)	text (number)										
265	s9q24c_shift	24c. Please provide the number of cadres working on a night shift Monday to Friday	text (number)										
266	s9q24d_shift	24d. Please provide duration of a night shift (Monday to Friday)	text										
267	s9q24e_shift	24e. Please specify professional cadres that are working on weekends (Saturday- Sunday)	text										
268	s9q24f_shift	24f. Please provide number of cadre working on a day shift on weekends	text (number)										
269	s9q24g_shift	24g. Please provide duration of a day shift on weekends	text										
270	s9q24h_shift	24h. Please provide the number of cadres working on a night shift on weekends	text (number)										
271	s9q24i_shift	24i. Please provide duration of a night shift on weekends	text										
272	s9q25_covid	25. Were there any changes in number, availability, organization and motivation of maternity and perinatal health staff in the hospital due to COVID-19? Please describe what have been done. Possible changes may relate to increase of staff to implement additional procedures, reduced availability because of staff infected and/or quarantined or shift composition? Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe.	notes										
273	hfa_section_9_perinatal_health_care_human_resource_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>Incomplete</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Unverified</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Complete</td></tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete				
0	Incomplete												
1	Unverified												
2	Complete												
Instrument: Hfa Section10 Maternity Ward Pharmacy Management Supplies (hfa_section10_maternity_ward_pharmacy_management_supplies)			^ Collapse										
274	s10q1_norm	Section Header: <i>SECTION 10. Maternity ward: Pharmacy management, supplies and medicine availability</i> 1. Describe the policy in place to make adequate drugs, consumables and appropriate instrument available for each normal delivery. What works perfectly? What is not working? What are the consequences? Why?	text, Required										
275	s10q2_eme	2. Describe the policy in place to make adequate drugs, consumables and appropriate instrument available for emergencies. What works perfectly? What is not working? What are the consequences? Why?	text, Required										
276	s10q3_cesa	3. Describe the policy in place to make adequate drugs, consumables and appropriate instrument available for C-sections. What works perfectly? What is not working? What are the consequences? Why?	text, Required										

277	s10q4_newb	4. Describe the policy in place to make adequate drugs, consumables and appropriate instrument available for newborn care. What works perfectly? What is not working? What are the consequences? Why?	text, Required						
278	s10q5_stor	5. Medication storage areas are orderly, clean and secure and with proper system	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
279	s10q6_tem	6. General medication storage is at room temperature unless there is a specific requirement for a particular medicine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
280	s10q7_cont	7. Cupboards and containers are available for storage	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
281	s10q8_prot	8. Medications are not stored on the floor or touching walls to protect from dampness and insects and rodents?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
282	s10q9_narc	9. Narcotics are kept in a separate locked cupboard	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
283	s10q10_chain	10. Cold chain is maintained for specific medications?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
284	s10q11_refr	11. Medication refrigerator temperature are maintained within acceptable limits?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
285	s10q12_ther	12. There are working thermometers in all refrigerators?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
286	s10q13_log	13. Storage temperature is recorded in a log at least daily?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
287	s10q14_ster	14. Sterilisation equipment functioning on day of visit? (observe in central facility)	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
288	s10q15_kit	15. How many sterilised delivery kits are available at time of visit? (document number seen)	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
289	s10q16_mark	16. Are they clearly marked as having been sterilised?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
290	s10q17_umb	17. What do you cut the umbilical cord with?	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Clamps</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Thread</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Other: [text]</td></tr> </table>	1	Clamps	2	Thread	3	Other: [text]
1	Clamps								
2	Thread								
3	Other: [text]								
291	s10q18_sut	18. Are there sterilised suturing kits with needles available for perinatal tears/episiotomy?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								

292	s10q19_tim Show the field ONLY if: [s10q18_sut]=1	19. How many at time of visit?	text (number), Required
293	s10q20_item	20. List the items routinely included in a delivery pack. (eg cord clamps, blade, scissors, sponge holding forceps, gauze,	text, Required
294	s10q22_shock	Section Header: <i>Postpartum hemorrhage</i> 22. Does the facility have the non-pneumatic anti-shock garments (NASG)?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
295	s10q23_ball	23. Do you have balloon or condom tamponade?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
296	s10q24_abd	24. Do you do abdominal packing material?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
297	s10q25_hyst	25. Can you do a hysterectomy?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
298	s10q26_lyn	26. Can you do B-Lynch suture techniques or similar and are the necessary supplies available ?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
299	s10q27_ultr	27. Is there a functioning ultrasound machine available for maternity ward use?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
300	s10q29_stet	Section Header: <i>Fetal heart monitoring equipment: list whether functioning devices available and how many on the day of your visit</i> 29. Pinard stethoscope	text, Required
301	s10q30_dop	30. Doppler devices	text, Required
302	s10q31_glo	31. Regular sterile gloves	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
303	s10q32_ster	32. Long sterile gloves (used for manual placenta removal)	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
304	s10q33_mask	33. Neonatal bag and mask resuscitation table with heating?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
305	s10q34_scis	34. Episiotomy scissors?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
306	s10q35_forc	35. Forceps?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
307	s10q36_suct	36. Suction apparatus (including mucus extractor)	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No
308	s10q37_vac	37. Vacuum extractor (manual, electric)?	yesno, Required 1 Yes 0 No

309	s10q38_man	38. Manual Vacuum Aspirator or D&C kit?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
310	s10q39_part	39. Blank partograph?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
311	s10q40_press	40. Functioning blood pressure machine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
312	s10q41_spec	41. Broad speculum	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
313	s10q42_spon	42. Sponge holding forceps	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
314	s10q43_spec	43. Gynecological speculum	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
315	s10q44_cesa	44. C-Section set	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
316	s10q45_hyst	45. Hysterectomy/laparotomy set	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
317	s10q46_light	46. Mobile light source for labour room	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
318	s10q47_sour	47. Light source for theatre	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
319	s10q48_resc	48. Newborn rescue table for labour room/theatre	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
320	s10q49_ther	49. Thermometer	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
321	s10q50_oxim	50. Pulse oximeter (Maternity, ICU/NCU/Theatre)	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
322	s10q51_prob	51. What are the problems, you usually face with drugs, consumables and equipment for normal deliveries, C-sections, emergencies and newborns care?	text, Required				
323	s10q52_covid	52. Were there any changes in pharmacy management, supplies and medicine availability due to COVID-19? Please describe what have been done. Possible changes may relate to new products added, or increase consumption of certain products with more frequent stock-out etc.? Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe.	descriptive				

324	hfa_section10_maternity_ward_pharmacy_management_supplies_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>Incomplete</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Unverified</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Complete</td></tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete			
0	Incomplete											
1	Unverified											
2	Complete											
Instrument: HFA Section 11: Laboratory Support (hfa_section_11_laboratory_support)			^ Collapse									
325	s11q1_glu	Section Header: <i>SECTION 11. Laboratory support</i> 1. Blood glucose	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
326	s11q1a_glu Show the field ONLY if: [s11q1_glu]=1	1a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
327	s11q1b_glu	1b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s11q1b_glu__1</td><td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s11q1b_glu__2</td><td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s11q1b_glu__3</td><td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td></tr> </table>	1	s11q1b_glu__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q1b_glu__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q1b_glu__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q1b_glu__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q1b_glu__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q1b_glu__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
328	s11q2_haem	2. Haemoglobin	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
329	s11q2a_haem Show the field ONLY if: [s11q2_haem]=1	2a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
330	s11q2b_haem	2b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s11q2b_haem__1</td><td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s11q2b_haem__2</td><td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s11q2b_haem__3</td><td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td></tr> </table>	1	s11q2b_haem__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q2b_haem__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q2b_haem__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q2b_haem__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q2b_haem__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q2b_haem__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
331	s11q3_pcv	3. Haematocrit (PCV)	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
332	s11q3a_pcv Show the field ONLY if: [s11q3_pcv]=1	3a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
333	s11q3b_pcv	3b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>s11q3b_pcv__1</td><td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>s11q3b_pcv__2</td><td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>s11q3b_pcv__3</td><td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td></tr> </table>	1	s11q3b_pcv__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q3b_pcv__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q3b_pcv__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q3b_pcv__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q3b_pcv__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q3b_pcv__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
334	s11q4_blo	4. Full blood count	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
335	s11q4a_blo Show the field ONLY if: [s11q4_blo]=1	4a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									

336	s11q4b_blo	4b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q4b_blo__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q4b_blo__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q4b_blo__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q4b_blo__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q4b_blo__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q4b_blo__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q4b_blo__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q4b_blo__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q4b_blo__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
337	s11q5_plat	5. Platelets	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
338	s11q5a_plat Show the field ONLY if: [s11q5_plat]=1	5a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
339	s11q5b_plat	5b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q5b_plat__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q5b_plat__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q5b_plat__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q5b_plat__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q5b_plat__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q5b_plat__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q5b_plat__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q5b_plat__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q5b_plat__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
340	s11q6_leuk	6. Leukocytes count	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
341	s11q6a_leuk Show the field ONLY if: [s11q6_leuk]=1	6a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
342	s11q6b_leuk	6b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q6b_leuk__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q6b_leuk__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q6b_leuk__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q6b_leuk__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q6b_leuk__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q6b_leuk__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q6b_leuk__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q6b_leuk__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q6b_leuk__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
343	s11q7_group	7. Blood grouping and cross-match	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
344	s11q7a_group Show the field ONLY if: [s11q7_group]=1	7a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
345	s11q7b_group	7b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q7b_group__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q7b_group__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q7b_group__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q7b_group__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q7b_group__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q7b_group__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q7b_group__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q7b_group__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q7b_group__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
346	s11q8_prot	8. Urine protein laboratory	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											

347	s11q8a_prot Show the field ONLY if: [s11q8_prot]=1	8a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
348	s11q8b_prot	8b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q8b_prot__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q8b_prot__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q8b_prot__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q8b_prot__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q8b_prot__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q8b_prot__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q8b_prot__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q8b_prot__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q8b_prot__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
349	s11q9_rap	9. Urine protein strips / rapid test	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
350	s11q9a_rap Show the field ONLY if: [s11q9_rap]=1	9a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
351	s11q9b_rap	9b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q9b_rap__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q9b_rap__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q9b_rap__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q9b_rap__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q9b_rap__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q9b_rap__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q9b_rap__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q9b_rap__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q9b_rap__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
352	s11q10_rhe	10. Rhesus antibodies	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
353	s11q10a_rhe Show the field ONLY if: [s11q10_rhe]=1	10a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
354	s11q10b_rhe	10b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q10b_rhe__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q10b_rhe__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q10b_rhe__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q10b_rhe__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q10b_rhe__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q10b_rhe__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q10b_rhe__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q10b_rhe__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q10b_rhe__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
355	s11q11_rdt	11. Malaria rapid test or blood smear	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
356	s11q11a_rdt Show the field ONLY if: [s11q11_rdt]=1	11a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
357	s11q11b_rdt	11b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q11b_rdt__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q11b_rdt__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q11b_rdt__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q11b_rdt__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q11b_rdt__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q11b_rdt__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q11b_rdt__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q11b_rdt__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q11b_rdt__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										

358	s11q12_hiv	12. HIV rapid test / PCR	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
359	s11q12a_hiv Show the field ONLY if: [s11q12_hiv]=1	12a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
360	s11q12b_hiv	12b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q12b_hiv__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q12b_hiv__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q12b_hiv__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q12b_hiv__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q12b_hiv__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q12b_hiv__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q12b_hiv__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q12b_hiv__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q12b_hiv__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
361	s11q13_liv	13. Liver function test	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
362	s11q13a_liv Show the field ONLY if: [s11q13_liv]=1	13a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
363	s11q13b_liv	13b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q13b_liv__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q13b_liv__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q13b_liv__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q13b_liv__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q13b_liv__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q13b_liv__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q13b_liv__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q13b_liv__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q13b_liv__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
364	s11q14_rena	14. Renal function test	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
365	s11q14a_rena Show the field ONLY if: [s11q14_rena]=1	14a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
366	s11q14b_rena	14b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q14b_rena__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q14b_rena__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q14b_rena__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q14b_rena__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q14b_rena__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q14b_rena__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q14b_rena__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q14b_rena__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q14b_rena__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
367	s11q15_crea	15. Creatinine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
368	s11q15a_crea Show the field ONLY if: [s11q15_crea]=1	15a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									

369	s11q15b_crea	15b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q15b_crea__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q15b_crea__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q15b_crea__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q15b_crea__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q15b_crea__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q15b_crea__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q15b_crea__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q15b_crea__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q15b_crea__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
370	s11q16_crp	16. C-reactive protein (CRP)	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
371	s11q16a_crp Show the field ONLY if: [s11q16_crp]=1	16a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
372	s11q16b_crp	16b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q16b_crp__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q16b_crp__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q16b_crp__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q16b_crp__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q16b_crp__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q16b_crp__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q16b_crp__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q16b_crp__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q16b_crp__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
373	s11q17_cult	17. Blood culture	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
374	s11q17a_cult Show the field ONLY if: [s11q17_cult]=1	17a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
375	s11q17b_cult	17b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q17b_cult__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q17b_cult__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q17b_cult__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q17b_cult__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q17b_cult__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q17b_cult__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q17b_cult__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q17b_cult__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q17b_cult__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
376	s11q18_sero	18. Serologic test for syphilis	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No					
1	Yes											
0	No											
377	s11q18a_sero Show the field ONLY if: [s11q18_sero]=1	18a. If yes, what is the average time from ordering to result available in maternity (in minutes)?	text, Required									
378	s11q18b_sero	18b. Which of these tests are done?	checkbox, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s11q18b_sero__1</td> <td>Routinely on admission to maternity ward?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s11q18b_sero__2</td> <td>For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s11q18b_sero__3</td> <td>For women with high blood pressure and seizures?</td> </tr> </table>	1	s11q18b_sero__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?	2	s11q18b_sero__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?	3	s11q18b_sero__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?
1	s11q18b_sero__1	Routinely on admission to maternity ward?										
2	s11q18b_sero__2	For women admitted with premature reupture of membranes and fever?										
3	s11q18b_sero__3	For women with high blood pressure and seizures?										
379	s11q19_unit	19. Blood: how many units of blood does the hospital have now? (including in the lab and blood bank)	text (number), Required									
380	s11q20_plas	20. Blood replacement - how many units of fresh frozen plasma and thrombocyte concentrate does the hospital have now?	text (number), Required									

381	s11q21_dona	21. What is the system of replacement currently practiced (routine blood donation from donor pool at hospital level, family replacement donors, national or zonal distribution)	text, Required						
382	s11q22_covid	22. Were there any changes in terms of laboratory support due to COVID-19? Please describe what have been done. Possible changes may relate to PCR availability, rapid tests availability, testing procedures? Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe. Possible changes may relate to the time it takes to get the results of the ordinary lab results. Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe.	notes, Required						
383	hfa_section_11_laboratory_support_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete
0	Incomplete								
1	Unverified								
2	Complete								
Instrument: Hfa Section12a Medicines Availability Checklist Longlist (hfa_section12a_medicines_availability_checklist_longlist) ^ Collapse									
384	s12aq1_ane	Section Header: <i>SECTION 12a. Medicines availability checklist (long list in hospital pharmacy)</i> 1. Spinal anaesthesia	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
385	s12aq2_hal	2. Halothane	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
386	s12aq3_ket	3. Ketamine injection	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
387	s12aq4_thio	4. Thiopental/Pentofale	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
388	s12aq5_oxy	5. Oxygen	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
389	s12aq6_lid	6. Lidocaine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
390	s12aq7_dia	7. Diazepam	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
391	s12aq8_mor	8. Morphine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
392	s12aq9_dexa	9. Dexamethasone	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
393	s12aq10_mag	10. Magnesium sulphate	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
394	s12aq11_hyd	11. Hydralazine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								

395	s12aq12_meth	12. Methyl dopa	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
396	s12aq13_ins	13. Insulin injection	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
397	s12aq14_melt	14. Metformin or glyburide	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
398	s12aq15_ergo	15. Ergometrine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
399	s12aq16_oxy	16. Oxytocin	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
400	s12aq17_mis	17. Misoprostol	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
401	s12aq18_mife	18. Mifepristone-misoprostol	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
402	s12aq19_tran	19. Tranexamic acid	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
403	s12aq20_nif	20. Nifedipine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
404	s12aq21_nifspe Show the field ONLY if: [s12aq20_nif]=1	21. Specify release formulation:	radio, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Immediate-release</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Slow release</td></tr> </table>	1	Immediate-release	2	Slow release		
1	Immediate-release								
2	Slow release								
405	hfa_section12a_medicines_availability_checklist_longlist_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>Incomplete</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Unverified</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Complete</td></tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete
0	Incomplete								
1	Unverified								
2	Complete								

Instrument: **Hfa Section12b Medicines Availability Checklist Short** (hfa_section12b_medicines_availability_checklist_short)

[^ Collapse](#)

406	s12bq1_oxyt	Section Header: <i>SECTION 12b. Medicines availability checklist (short list in maternity ward)</i> 1. Oxytocin	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
407	s12bq2_oxytf Show the field ONLY if: [s12bq1_oxyt]=1	2. If oxytocin available, was it in a fridge?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
408	s12bq3_miso	3. Misoprostol	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
409	s12bq4_lid	4. Lidocaine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						

410	s12bq5_mag	5. Magnesium sulphate	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
411	s12bq6_acid	6. Tranexamic acid	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
412	s12bq7_hyd	7. Hydralazine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
413	s12bq8_nife	8. Nifedipine	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
414	s12qb9_firs	9. First line hypertensives	yesno <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
415	s12bq10_use	9. Which are the first line anti-hypertensives that you use?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
416	s12bq11_ant	10. Are prophylactic antibiotics used for all patients irrespective of indication?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
417	s12bq12_giv	11. If yes, what is usually given?	text, Required						
418	s12bq13_spon	12. Are prophylactic antibiotics used for In labour with spontaneous rupture of membranes for four hours or more? No fever or other signs of infection?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
419	s12bq14_giv	13. If yes, what is usually given?	text, Required						
420	s12bq15_rupt	14. Are prophylactic antibiotics used for In labour with rupture of membrane for four hours or more? With fever or other signs of infection?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
421	s12bq16_giv	15. If yes, what is usually given?	text, Required						
422	s12bq17_cesa	16. Are prophylactic antibiotics used for Elective C-section <i>16 s12bq16_cesa Are prophylactic antibiotics used for Elective C-section Y / N Break down by prophylaxis (eg a dose at maternity, in theatre) or after surgery, eg some facilities routinely give 3-5 days of treatment dose antibiotics</i>	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
423	s12bq18_giv	17. If yes, what is usually given?	text, Required						
424	s12bq19_eme	18. Are prophylactic antibiotics used for Non-scheduled (emergency) C-section <i>Break down by prophylaxis (eg a dose in maternity or theatre) or after surgery, eg some facilities routinely give 3-5 days of treatment dose antibiotics</i>	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
425	s12bq20_giv	19. If yes, what is usually given?	text, Required						
426	s12bq21_inf	20. What first line antibiotics do you use for neonatal infections?	text, Required						
427	s12bq22_covid	22. Were there any changes in terms of drugs required to be available due to COVID-19? Please describe what have been done. Possible changes may relate dexamethasone. Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe.	notes, Required						
428	hfa_section12b_medicines_availability_checklist_short_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>Incomplete</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Unverified</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Complete</td></tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete
0	Incomplete								
1	Unverified								
2	Complete								

Instrument: HFA Section13: Procedures Guidelines Standards (hfa_section13_procedures_guidelines_standards)		^ Collapse							
429	s13q1_hem	Section Header: <i>SECTION 13. Procedures/Guidelines/standards Please provide name of guidelines, protocols or documents present for each thematic area:</i> 1. Postpartum haemorrhage	text, Required						
430	s13q2_ecl	2. (Pre) eclampsia	text, Required						
431	s13q3_lab	3. Management of premature labour/birth	text, Required						
432	s13q4_res	4. Neonatal resuscitation	text, Required						
433	s13q5_sep	5. Sepsis (anteartum, intrapartum, postpartum; newborn)	text, Required						
434	s13q6_kang	6. Kangaroo care (KMC)	text, Required						
435	s13q7_neo	7. Neonatal care	text, Required						
436	s13q8_prev	8. Infection prevention and control (IPC)	text, Required						
437	s13q9_pmtct	9. PMTCT	text, Required						
438	s13q10_moth	10. Postnatal care - mother	text, Required						
439	s13q11_bab	11. Postnatal care - baby	text, Required						
440	s13q12_sop	12. Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for C-section	text, Required						
441	s13q13_surg	13. WHO Surgical Checklist	text, Required						
442	s13q14_anes	14. WHO checklist for safe anesthesia	text, Required						
443	s13q15_inc	15. SOP incoming referrals	text, Required						
444	s13q16_out	16. SOP out-going referrals	text, Required						
445	s13q17_brea	17. Breastfeeding?	text, Identifier						
446	s13q18_fam	18. Postpartum family planning?	text, Required						
447	s13q19_dang	19. When discharged, what danger signs are women told to seek treatment for about themselves and about the newborn's health?	text, Required						
448	s13q20_adv	20. When discharged, what advice are women given about postpartum hygiene?	text, Required						
449	s13q21_surv	21. Maternal and perinatal death surveillance and response (MPDSR)	text, Required						
450	s13q22_covid	22. Were there any changes implemented in terms of guidelines and protocols in the way to adapt due to COVID-19? Please describe what have been done.	text, Required						
451	s13q23_covid	23. During the past month, did you issue locally updated clinical care guidelines about the provision of care during childbirth. Did you receive any from authorities or from any other external organization?	text, Required						
452	s13q24_covid	24. During the past six months, did your facility or ward provide maternity ward providers with any training on COVID-19, for example simulations or drills?	yesno, Required <table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
453	s13q25_covid	25. At this time, what is done in practice for suspected case of COVID19 in general and particularly for pregnant women suspected to have COVID19? Comment on who pay for the different procedures? What is paid by patient and how much?	notes, Required						
454	s13q26_covid	26. Did you implement any other change?	notes, Required						
455	s13q27_covid	27. Did you implement any changes in relation to breastfeeding? Please describe	notes, Required						
456	s13q28_covid	28. Did you implement any other changes, if yes, please describe? Probe: - Number of antenatal care visits during pregnancy - Changes in length of stay after childbirth?	notes, Required						
457	hfa_section13_procedures_guidelines_standards_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete
0	Incomplete								
1	Unverified								
2	Complete								

Instrument: HFA Section14: Qi Practices In Place (hfa_section14_qi_practices_in_place) ^ Collapse							
458	s14q1_rev	Section Header: <i>SECTION 14. Qi practices in place</i> 1. Do you conduct maternal death reviews? How often? When did it start? Please comment	text, Required				
459	s14q2_peri	2. Do you conduct perinatal death reviews? How often? When did it start? Please comment (who is in charge? How does it work? etc.) Probe specifically whether stillbirths included	text, Required				
460	s14q3_miss	3. Do you conduct maternal near-miss reviews? How often? What year these reviews began in this hospital? Please comment (who is in charge? How does it work? etc.)	text, Required				
461	s14q4_start	4. Do you conduct perinatal near-miss reviews? How often? When did it start? Please comment (who is in charge? How does it work? etc.)	text, Required				
462	s14q5_qigo	5. How many quality improvement initiatives exist in the hospital at the moment or have been terminated less than 3 years ago?	text (number, Min: 0, Max: 10), Required				
463	s14q5a_qigo1 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=1	5a. What is the name of the QI initiative?	text, Required				
464	s14q5b_qigo1 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=1	5b. When did it start?	text, Required				
465	s14q5c_qigo1 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=1	5c. Is it ongoing?	yesno, Required <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
466	s14q5d_qigo1 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=1 and [s14q5c_qigo1]=0	5d. If you answered 'no' to the previous question please indicate when it ended?	text, Required				
467	s14q5e_qigo1 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=1	5e. Please describe the focus, methods and results of this initiative	text, Required				
468	s14q5f_qigo1 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=1	5f. Who is in charge of this initiative?	text, Required				
469	s14q5g_qigo1 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=1	5g. Are there additional comments?	text, Required				
470	s14q6a_qigo2 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=2	6a. What is the name of the QI initiative?	text, Required				
471	s14q6b_qigo2 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=2	6b. When did it start?	text, Required				
472	s14q6c_qigo2 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=2	6c. Is it ongoing?	yesno, Required <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
473	s14q6d_qigo2 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=2 and [s14q6c_qigo2]=0	6d. If you answered 'no' to the previous question please indicate when it ended?	text, Required				
474	s14q6e_qigo2 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=2	6e. Please describe the focus, methods and results of this initiative	text, Required				

475	s14q6f_qigo2 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=2	6f. Who is in charge of this initiative?	text, Required				
476	s14q6g_qigo2 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=2	6g. Are there additional comments?	text, Required				
477	s14q7a_qigo3 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=3	7a. What is the name of the QI initiative?	text, Required				
478	s14q7b_qigo3 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=3	7b. When did it start?	text, Required				
479	s14q7c_qigo3 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=3	7c. Is it ongoing?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
480	s14q7d_qigo3 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=3 and [s14q7c_qigo3]=0	7d. If you answered 'no' to the previous question please indicate when it ended?	text, Required				
481	s14q7e_qigo3 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=3	7e. Please describe the focus, methods and results of this initiative	text, Required				
482	s14q7f_qigo3 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=3	7f. Who is in charge of this initiative?	text, Required				
483	s14q7g_qigo3 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=3	7g. Are there additional comments?	text, Required				
484	s14q8a_qigo4 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=4	8a. What is the name of the QI initiative?	text, Required				
485	s14q8b_qigo4 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=4	8b. When did it start?	text, Required				
486	s14q8c_qigo4 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=4	8c. Is it ongoing?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
487	s14q8d_qigo4 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=4 and [s14q8c_qigo4]=0	8d. If you answered 'no' to the previous question please indicate when it ended?	text, Required				
488	s14q8e_qigo4 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=4	8e. Please describe the focus, methods and results of this initiative	text, Required				
489	s14q8f_qigo4 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=4	8f. Who is in charge of this initiative?	text, Required				
490	s14q8g_qigo4 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=4	8g. Are there additional comments?	text, Required				
491	s14q9a_qigo5 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=5	9a. What is the name of the QI initiative?	text, Required				

492	s14q9b_qigo5 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=5	9b. When did it start?	text, Required				
493	s14q9c_qigo5 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=5	9c. Is it ongoing?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
494	s14q9d_qigo5 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=5 and [s14q9c_qigo5]=0	9d. If you answered 'no' to the previous question please indicate when it ended?	text, Required				
495	s14q9e_qigo5 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=5	9e. Please describe the focus, methods and results of this initiative	text, Required				
496	s14q9f_qigo5 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=5	9f. Who is in charge of this initiative?	text, Required				
497	s14q9g_qigo5 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=5	9g. Are there additional comments?	text, Required				
498	s14q10a_qigo6 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=6	10a. What is the name of the QI initiative?	text, Required				
499	s14q10b_qigo6 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=6	10b. When did it start?	text, Required				
500	s14q10c_qigo6 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=6	10c. Is it ongoing?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
501	s14q10d_qigo6 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=6 and [s14q10c_qigo6]=0	10d. If you answered 'no' to the previous question please indicate when it ended?	text, Required				
502	s14q10e_qigo6 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=6	10e. Please describe the focus, methods and results of this initiative	text, Required				
503	s14q10f_qigo6 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=6	10f. Who is in charge of this initiative?	text, Required				
504	s14q10g_qigo6 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=6	10g. Are there additional comments?	text, Required				
505	s14q11a_qigo7 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=7	11a. What is the name of the QI initiative?	text, Required				
506	s14q11b_qigo7 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=7	11b. When did it start?	text, Required				
507	s14q11c_qigo7 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=7	11c. Is it ongoing?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						

508	s14q11d_qigo7 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=7 and [s14q11c_qigo7]=0	11d. If you answered 'no' to the previous question please indicate when it ended?	text, Required				
509	s14q11e_qigo7 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=7	11e. Please describe the focus, methods and results of this initiative	text, Required				
510	s14q11f_qigo7 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=7	11f. Who is in charge of this initiative?	text, Required				
511	s14q11g_qigo7 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=7	11g. Are there additional comments?	text, Required				
512	s14q12a_qigo8 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=8	12a. What is the name of the QI initiative?	text, Required				
513	s14q12b_qigo8 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=8	12b. When did it start?	text, Required				
514	s14q12c_qigo8 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=8	12c. Is it ongoing?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
515	s14q12d_qigo8 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=8 and [s14q12c_qigo8]=0	12d. If you answered 'no' to the previous question please indicate when it ended?	text, Required				
516	s14q12e_qigo8 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=8	12e. Please describe the focus, methods and results of this initiative	text, Required				
517	s14q12f_qigo8 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=8	12f. Who is in charge of this initiative?	text, Required				
518	s14q12g_qigo8 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=8	12g. Are there additional comments?	text, Required				
519	s14q13a_qigo9 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=9	13a. What is the name of the QI initiative?	text, Required				
520	s14q13b_qigo9 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=9	13b. When did it start?	text, Required				
521	s14q13c_qigo9 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=9	13c. Is it ongoing?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes						
0	No						
522	s14q13d_qigo9 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=9 and [s14q13c_qigo9]=0	13d. If you answered 'no' to the previous question please indicate when it ended?	text, Required				
523	s14q13e_qigo9 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=9	13e. Please describe the focus, methods and results of this initiative	text, Required				
524	s14q13f_qigo9 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=9	13f. Who is in charge of this initiative?	text, Required				

525	s14q13g_qigo9 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]>=9	13g. Are there additional comments?	text, Required						
526	s14q14a_qigo10 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]=10	14a. What is the name of the QI initiative?	text, Required						
527	s14q14b_qigo10 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]=10	14b. When did it start?	text, Required						
528	s14q14c_qigo10 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]=10	14c. Is it ongoing?	yesno, Required <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes								
0	No								
529	s14q14d_qigo10 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]=10 and [s14q14c_qigo10]=0	14d. If you answered 'no' to the previous question please indicate when it ended?	text, Required						
530	s14q14e_qigo10 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]=10	14e. Please describe the focus, methods and results of this initiative	text, Required						
531	s14q14f_qigo10 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]=10	14f. Who is in charge of this initiative?	text, Required						
532	s14q14g_qigo10 Show the field ONLY if: [s14q5_qigo]=10	14g. Are there additional comments?	text, Required						
533	s14q15_covid	15. Were there any changes in the ability to implement quality improvement activities due to COVID-19? Please describe what have been done. Possible changes may relate to reduced ability to perform maternal deaths reviews because ♦Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe and share how this happened and influenced the quality improvement activities.	text						
534	hfa_section14_qi_practices_in_place_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete
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Instrument: HFA Section15: Interactions With The Community (hfa_section15_interactions_with_the_community)			^ Collapse						
535	s15q1_pol	Section Header: <i>SECTION 15. Interactions with the community</i> 1. Describe any existing policies/strategies to collect routinely information on user's satisfaction or experiences	text						
536	s15q2_for	2. With specific focus on maternity care, Is there a Safe Motherhood Committee or other community/ stakeholder forum serving this hospital catchment area? Please describe and comment	text						
537	s15q3_covidcom	3. Has your facility published or distributed any materials (brochure, flier, posters, etc) about COVID-19 targeted toward pregnant, laboring/delivering, or postnatal women?	notes						

538	s15q4_covidform	4. In what form is this information provided? (select all that apply)	checkbox <table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>s15q4_covidform__1</td> <td>Health talks</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>s15q4_covidform__2</td> <td>Leaflets/fliers</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>s15q4_covidform__3</td> <td>Posters</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>s15q4_covidform__4</td> <td>Counseling during consultations</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>s15q4_covidform__5</td> <td>Facility website</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>s15q4_covidform__6</td> <td>Phone line with advice</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>s15q4_covidform__7</td> <td>Social Media (WhatsApp, Facebook, Emails etc.)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>s15q4_covidform__8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	s15q4_covidform__1	Health talks	2	s15q4_covidform__2	Leaflets/fliers	3	s15q4_covidform__3	Posters	4	s15q4_covidform__4	Counseling during consultations	5	s15q4_covidform__5	Facility website	6	s15q4_covidform__6	Phone line with advice	7	s15q4_covidform__7	Social Media (WhatsApp, Facebook, Emails etc.)	8	s15q4_covidform__8	Other
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8	s15q4_covidform__8	Other																									
539	s15q4a_covidformoth Show the field ONLY if: [s15q4_covidform(8)]=1	4a. If you chose other to the previous question, please specify	text, Required																								
540	s15q5_covidany	5. Were there any other changes in how he hospital interact with the community due to COVID-19? Please describe what have changed. Possible changes may relate to increased communication using various channels, reduced involvement of the community in hospitals management, poorer functioning of community engagement platforms etc. Did you observe such kind of change in this hospital? please describe.	text																								
541	hfa_section15_interactions_wi th_the_community_complete	Section Header: <i>Form Status</i> Complete?	dropdown <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete																		
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Instrument: **HFA Section 16: Drawing Maps Of Hospital Maternal Care** (hfa_section_16_drawing_maps_of_hospital_maternal_c) [^ Collapse](#)

542	s16q1_maph	<p>Section Header: <i>Section 16. Draw an approximate map of the areas related to maternal care provision within the hospital</i></p> <p>1. Instructions: Please now ask to be shown around the hospital with a key focus to map the location of the maternity ward and related areas. Where necessary add any possible distance information (even if approximate) in meters, in number of stairs etc.</p> <p>Map locate all the places that are used by health staff, women and newborns for provision of care and for their other needs in the hospital.</p> <p>(1) Entrance to the hospital which is used by women arriving in labour: if you arrive at the hospital entrance, is there a clear sign where to go? Many women are illiterate, is there also a picture / icon indicating? I do not think so FIELD NOTES!!!! And Pictues</p> <p>(2) Entrance to the hospital which is used by ambulances/vehicles bringing maternity referrals</p> <p>(3) OPD (if multiple locations, then mark where routine outpatient antenatal care provided and where emergency care for pregnant women is provided if any). In some places at night all pregnant women are directly sent to maternity for triage and treatment, in other places they go via OPD like all other clients.</p> <p>(4) Inpatient antenatal ward</p> <p>(5) RCH (routine ANC and outpatient PNC)</p> <p>(6) Labour ward/room</p> <p>(7) Dedicated c-section theatre (if exists) or general operating theatres used for c-sections</p> <p>(8) Postnatal care ward</p> <p>(9) NICU/newborn ward/KMC ward</p> <p>(10) Maternity waiting area/home (where women live before they are admitted)</p> <p>(11) Cashier/registration</p> <p>(12) Laboratory</p> <p>(13) Pharmacy</p> <p>(14) Blood bank</p> <p>(15) Archive</p> <p>(16) Kitchen or cooking area used by mothers and their companions</p> <p>(17) Laundry area used by mothers and companions</p> <p>(18) Sharps pit, Placenta pit</p> <p>(19) Location of well or borehole (if no centrally piped water source)</p> <p>(20) Ultrasound room if any</p> <p>(21) Mortuary??</p> <p>(22) CTC (HIV/AIDS Care and Treatment Centre)</p>	file, Required
543	s16q2_mapm	<p>2. Now draw a map of the maternity ward, and locate the following elements on it.</p> <p>(1) Admission desk</p> <p>(2) Midwife table/station(s)</p> <p>(3) Sink or bucket with running water</p> <p>(4) Toilets (indicate those only for staff versus those available to mothers)</p> <p>(5) Showers</p> <p>(6) Beds and partitions/doors - Differential beds for 1st stage of labour and 2nd stage (delivery beds). Please pay particular attention to privacy, noting doors and partitions, and whether the available means to ensuring privacy are being used at the time of your visit.</p> <p>(7) Medicine cabinets</p> <p>(8) Medical waste</p> <p>(9) Sterilised delivery kits</p> <p>(10) High level disinfection</p> <p>(11) Heated area for newborn resuscitation</p> <p>(12) Place where companions wait</p> <p>(13) Location(s) of patient files while in the ward</p>	file
544	s16q3_mapp	3. Now draw a map of the postnatal ward	file

545	s16q4_mapn	<p>4. Now the NICU</p> <p>Can you comment on the distance and difficulty of access between the following locations: Please note on a drawing or in writing if these locations are in different building, on a different floor (how many stairs), whether the walkway is covered and lit at night.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Labour ward and Operation Theater (where C-sections are performed). Is it possible to wheel a patient on a wheelchair or a bed? - Labour ward and NICU (and any other locations with newborns such as KMC ward) - OT and NICU (and any other locations with newborns such as KMC ward) - Postnatal ward and NICU (and any other locations with newborns such as KMC ward) - Where sterile equipment is stored and OT - Labour ward and laboratory 	file						
546	hfa_section_16_drawing_map_s_of_hospital_maternal_c_complete	<p>Section Header: <i>Form Status</i></p> <p>Complete?</p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete
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<p>Instrument: HFA Section17: Details Of The Visit (hfa_section17_details_of_the_visit) ^ Collapse</p>									
547	s17q1	<p>Section Header: <i>Section 17. DETAILS OF THE VISIT</i></p> <p>1. Number of visits needed to complete the form</p>	text, Required						
548	s17q2_dat	2. Date of visit 1	text (date_dmy), Required						
549	s17q3_wp4lead	3. Name of WP4 focal point or consortium member collecting the data	text, Required						
550	s17q4_assenum	4. Name of quantitative data enumerator(s) assisting in the data collection	text, Required						
551	s17q5_comm	<p>5. Comments on all the visit</p> <p><i>Not required, but this is very important. Please note if you had any other person with you during the visit, or any other issues (long periods of time during visit waiting, etc). Be detailed as possible to allow learning from the process.</i></p>	descriptive						
552	hfa_section17_details_of_the_visit_complete	<p>Section Header: <i>Form Status</i></p> <p>Complete?</p>	<p>dropdown</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unverified</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Complete</td> </tr> </table>	0	Incomplete	1	Unverified	2	Complete
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